

**ORGANIZATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING IN HIGHER
EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND INTRODUCTION OF SPEECH
UNITS FOR STUDENTS****Jamoliddinova Mohinur Davlatjonovna**

Student of foreign language and literature (English) direction,
Faculty of english language and literature
Fergana State University

Axmadalieva Dildora

Lecturer of english language and literature faculty
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The fact that social changes in society in recent years have been interpreted as one of the most important issues affecting the future development of our society, the issue of training mature personnel, which can meet the demand of the times, requires the implementation of significant changes in the educational process. In education, the process of integralization with the world community, Ham has created opportunities to use new teaching technologies abroad, rich experience. In addition, it is now assumed to use the achievements of Science and technology, especially those achieved in linguistics, pedagogy, didactics, psycholinguistics and psychology, to increase the effectiveness of the educational process.

Currently, another of the most relevant issues in education is the provision of knowledge and the implementation of an educational goal based on the purpose of teaching, content, methods, tools, organizational images and the material of the science being studied in the teaching process.

New-new directions in Language Teaching have been influenced by approach and method. But, this method in language teaching, approaches to teaching, has not yet been able to reveal the fundamental essence of the language. the approach and methods that arose served to teach one or another area of the language, only. No theory, approach or methods covered the general facets of Language Teaching. Nevertheless, Language Teaching has now reached the methanazarian stage. As a result, the language began to be interpreted on the basis of anthropocentric theory at a new stage. In it, as a central figure, man began to be understood.

The issue of the personality factor in the creation and perception of interaction in teaching a foreign language in the coverage of such areas of modern linguistics as linguopragmatics, linguoculturology, Psycholinguistics,

cognitive linguistics, ethnolinguistics, discursive analysis forms the center of the object of instruction.

The success and effectiveness of teaching a foreign language in non-philological higher educational institutions is characterized by psychological and pedagogical factors associated with the beginning of teaching a foreign language in the University and its organization. In non-philological higher educational institutions, what a foreign language is like is a link to how much higher education is organized and conducted in the initial boskich.

Scientific literature and methodological instructions on differentiating the stages of teaching a foreign language in non-philological higher educational institutions, the cited opinion is based on the results of pedagogical practice and observation of student students in the course of the lesson, it can be said that when choosing educational material for the first academic year, when determining methods of working with this language material, That is, to begin with, all of the work described above should be carried out in such a way that the student has acquired age characteristics and his worldview.

It should not be forgotten that reading and learning is an activity based on painstaking cocktails. Therefore, in the formation of oral speech at the initial stage of higher education, that is, in the cultivation of speech skills, students should not take their knowledge in a ready state and remember it, but to shape them on the basis of activities that require a certain cocktail. Such activity should be an activity in students that requires a certain initiative, mental and physical exertion, that is, Harakat. During this activity, students hiss to get used to their participation in the speech process, which in them personifies positive emotionality and instills confidence in their own forces. Taking into account the interests of students in the course of the lesson, they should not be ignored, at the same time they should be taught to go through various obstacles, difficulties. Therefore, working with students who do not have a foreign language specialty requires initiative, resourcefulness and incessant search from the student.

Also when growing a student's speech, it is necessary to always aosure taffakur. The student's careful observation, attention to comprehension, memorization, and observation with analysis related to species division, generalization, systematization explanation, and proof of conduct will ensure that speech is cultivated in the taffacur-based field. It is a little easy for a student to say what he has studied in a foreign language without a plan, but the teacher must teach him to draw up a plan of his own story, divide the text he studied into parts, and make it possible to write a letter in each part, to make

him accustomed to stating it in a certain In addition to cultivating students ' speech and thinking skills, it is required to pay attention to the cultivation of their written speech , to the fact that they can write their thoughts literately in accordance with their level. Teacher before organizing written actions:

- 1) conducting an approximate orthographic readiness to prevent error;
- 2) the student's ability to use dictionaries;
- 3) creative work should be gradually complicated.

In order to master the types of speech activity in a foreign language well, it is required to increase the student's vocabulary, learn phrases in the language, and at the same time, master the grammar of the language. Memory is well preserved when students hear new words or phrases about a foreign language. Experiments have shown that when a student skips the words of a foreign language he is studying many times in circulation, then chukur settles in memory. In this case, it is only in the presence of a new word or phrase that the construction of a sentence is hopeful to maxad. In addition, learning to write words in a side notebook gives Ham a good result. Stagnant compounds, stable phrases, Proverbs occupy a large place in the treasury of the language, making nutk content, attractive, while increasing the student's language wealth. When a student whose speech is not fluent is able to master the lesson well, Ham is dressed in an oral answer, in which the student does not seem to be well prepared for the lesson. It is necessary to force such students to communicate a lot in a foreign language. In particular, memorizing vokea –khikoyas on a foreign language, as well as lions, texts, dialogues and monologues, will give a good result. It is worth saying that in order to improve the speech of students, it is recommended that a student who has knowledge of oral and written speech attend various conferences and give a speech in a foreign language, make a report so that the skills can be mastered in Kham.

In conclusion, in the process of organizing the teaching of a foreign language, the problem of the image of the external world in the human psychological imagination and its reflection in the language is one of the pressing problems when teaching foreign language learners to speak a foreign language, their language and speech reserves, the memorization of each other by units concentrated in them, checking These problems create the need to implement language and speech units in the associative direction in the teaching of linguistics and foreign language.

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